

(DAS) for May and Dec sown crops and at 57 DAS for the Jun crop.

S. aculeata and *S. rostrum* had similar performance irrespective of date of sowing (Table 1, 2). The May-sown crop performed best (May is the most appropriate time for growing a green manure crop to fit local rice-based cropping systems). The Jun-sown crop had reduced plant height and less biomass production. The Dec crops had very poor growth. □

Biofertilizer efficiency in lowland rice

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We studied the efficiency of blue-green algae, Azospirillum, and azolla alone and with 50, 75, and 100 kg N/ha during wet and dry seasons 1986-87. Treatments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

Azospirillum lipoferum at 10^8 cells/g inoculant was inoculated at 1 kg/ha by seedling root dip for 20 min. A composite culture of blue-green algae was applied in the soil at 10 kg/ha 10 d after transplanting (DT). *Azolla pinnata* was established as dual crop at 1 t/ha 10 DT and the azolla mat incorporated at 20 d and 40 d.

Effect of biofertilizers on grain yield. Madurai, India, 1986-87.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kharif (CO 37)	Rabi (IR20)
100 kg N/ha alone	5.9	4.2
75 kg N/ha alone	5.7	6.0
50 kg N/ha alone	5.0	3.8
75 kg N/ha + blue-green algae	6.2	4.5
75 kg N/ha + azolla	5.9	4.5
75 kg N/ha + Azospirillum	6.4	4.5
50 kg N/ha + blue-green algae	5.6	4.0
50 kg N/ha + azolla	5.2	4.1
50 kg N/ha + Azospirillum	5.9	4.0
Blue-green algae alone	4.8	3.2
Azolla alone	4.6	3.3
Azospirillum alone	4.9	3.3
No fertilizer control	4.1	2.8
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.3

Azospirillum with 75 kg N/ha influenced grain yield the most, with a significant increase in wet season rice and a dry season yield comparable to that with 100 kg N/ha (see table). In

both seasons, yields with blue-green algae and 75 kg N/ha or dual cropping of azolla, and that with Azospirillum with 50 kg N/ha were comparable with yield with 100 kg N/ha. □

Effect of Azospirillum biofertilizer on rice yield

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We compared the effect of Azospirillum biofertilizer with that of organic manure

at various levels of N during kharif (Jun-Sep) and rabi (Oct-Feb) 1986-87. Test varieties were IR50 in kharif and IR20 in rabi. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications.

Soil was a sandy loam with pH 6.8, EC 0.43 dS/m, and 297-40-153 kg available NPK/ha. Farmyard manure

Table 1. Productive tillers and grain yield with organic manure and Azospirillum application at 4 N levels.^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./m ²)					Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean
Control	487	531	549	566	533	3.2	3.8	3.9	4.1	3.8
5 t FYM/ha	501	544	556	572	543	3.3	3.7	4.0	4.4	3.9
Azospirillum (nursery + main field)	535	550	556	564	551	3.3	3.9	4.1	4.2	3.8
FYM + Azospirillum	489	521	550	576	534	3.2	3.8	4.1	4.5	3.9
Mean	503	536	553	569		3.3	3.8	4.0	4.3	
						LSD		LSD		
						FYM × Azospirillum		ns		
						Levels of N		0.2		
						FYM × Azospirillum × N level		ns		

^aN applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha = 100% N.

Table 2. Productive tillers and grain yield as influenced by organic manure and Azospirillum at 4 N levels.^a Tamil Nadu, 1986 rabi.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./m ²)					Grain yield (t/ha)				
	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean	No N	49 kg N/ha	73 kg N/ha	98 kg N/ha	Mean
Control	334	357	378	406	369	2.9	3.6	3.9	4.1	3.6
5 t FYM/ha	335	367	373	385	365	2.7	3.7	4.1	3.9	3.6
Azospirillum (seed + nursery + root dip + main field)	351	370	364	453	385	3.1	4.0	4.0	4.4	3.9
FYM + Azospirillum	380	367	392	454	398	3.0	3.8	4.0	4.6	3.9
Mean	350	365	377	425		2.9	3.8	4.0	4.3	
						LSD		LSD		
						FYM × Azospirillum		21		
						Levels of N		16		
						FYM × Azospirillum × N level		32		

^aN applied per soil test recommendation, with 98 kg N/ha = 100% N.